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Abstract

Callus tissue exhibits a viscoelastic behaviour that has a strong influence on the distribution of stresses and their evolution with time and, thus, it can affect tissue differentiation during distraction procedures. For this reason, a deep knowledge of that viscoelastic behaviour can be very useful to improve current protocols of bone distraction and bone transport.

Monitoring stress relaxation of the callus during distraction osteogenesis allows characterizing its viscoelastic behaviour. Different procedures have been used in the literature to fit the response of a given viscoelastic model to the force relaxation curve. However, these procedures do not ensure the uniqueness of that fit, which is of the utmost importance for statistical purposes. This work uses a fitting procedure already validated for other tissues that ensures that uniqueness. Very importantly too, the procedure presented here allows obtaining more information from the stress relaxation tests, distinguishing relaxation in different time scales, which provides a deeper insight into the viscoelastic behaviour and its evolution over time.

As it was observed in the results, relaxation is faster at the first days after osteotomy and becomes slower and more gradual with time. This fact can be directly linked to the temporal evolution of the callus composition (water, organic phase and mineral content) and also to the progression of tissue differentiation, with a prevalence of hard tissues as time passes.

Keywords

Distraction osteogenesis, bone transport, callus relaxation force, viscoelasticity

Introduction

It is well documented that stresses in the callus relax with time after distraction as a viscoelastic material would do in a stress relaxation test^{1,2}. For that reason it is reasonable to use viscoelastic models to characterise the mechanical behaviour of the callus. A proper characterisation of this time-dependent behaviour is key to achieve a better estimation of stress distribution within the callus that would allow a deeper knowledge of the correlation between stresses/strains and tissue differentiation during the distraction process. A better understanding of the viscoelastic behaviour of bone callus could also help to improve the current protocols of bone distraction and its application to bone transport^{3,4}, by considering the effect of induced vibrations, distraction patterns, variations of these patterns with the time elapsed from osteotomy (TEFO), etc.

Some bone transport studies have measured the forces produced during bone segment distraction^{3,4}, though these works did not provide long term forces from which relaxation measurements could be extracted. More recently, Mora-Macías et al.⁵ have fitted a viscoelastic model to the stress relaxation measured in bone transport experiments conducted in sheep. In the present work, we have fitted those experiments using an alternative protocol that presents certain advantages with respect to that used in Mora-Macías et al.⁵. To be precise, it ensures the uniqueness of the fit

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and consequently allows a more robust statistical analysis. More importantly, it provides insight on the stress relaxation at different time scales, which can be correlated to the callus composition. This alternative protocol has been previously published and tested for other tissues such as cartilage and adipose tissue⁶⁻⁸.

The main objectives of this work are: 1) to show that this alternative protocol can be used to characterize the stress relaxation in distraction of bone transport callus; 2) to show its advantages in the interpretation of the data; and 3) to study the evolution of the viscoelastic properties of bone transport callus with TEFO.

Methods

Experimental force measurements

A set of experimental force measurements of bone segment distraction obtained in a previous work⁵ has been used here. Experiments consisted in applying bone transport using an instrumented Ilizarov-type distractor⁹⁻¹¹ implanted on the metatarsus of 7 merino sheep. Two osteotomies were performed in the metatarsus to create a gap of 15 mm and an additional osteotomy to separate the transportable segment. The instrumented distractor was implanted after the osteotomies and the transportable segment was moved 1mm per day for 15 days during the distraction phase to fill the generated defect (a scheme of the procedure is shown in Fig. 1).

The relaxation of the callus force during the whole process of bone transport was monitored (100 Hz) by the load cells mounted in the bars of the distractor. As explained in Mora-Macías et al.⁵, a minimum of 8 force relaxation measurements were performed per animal during the 15 days of distraction, thus making a total of 64 measurements, though the measurements days did not coincide for all sheep, as can be seen in Fig. 4. The force acquisition during relaxation was limited to the 10 minutes that followed the

distraction on each day. During that time, the animal was laid on the floor under anesthesia (xylazine) to eliminate likely alterations of the relaxation forces due to muscular activity. Finally, only 5 minutes were used to fit the curves because the rest of the recording was discarded as some sheep started to move after that time, as anaesthesia was wearing off. The reader is referred to Mora-Macías et al.⁵ for a more detailed explanation of the experimental procedure.

Fitting algorithm

We use here the quasi-linear viscoelastic (QLV) formulation proposed by Fung¹². The force response, $F(\lambda, t)$, to a stretch step $\lambda = \lambda_0 \cdot H(t)$ (with $H(t)$ the Heaviside function) is factorized using a reduced relaxation function, $\bar{G}(t)$, that accounts for the temporal evolution of stresses, and an elastic response function, $T^{(e)}(\lambda)$, that accounts for the relationship between stresses and strains and can be a general non-linear function:

$$F(\lambda, t) = \bar{G}(t) T^{(e)}(\lambda) \quad (1)$$

A distraction step can be approximated by a stretch step, $\lambda = \lambda_0$ which was kept constant for a whole day. In such case, $T^{(e)}(\lambda)$ is constant and, if a linear elastic behaviour is assumed, it corresponds to the force applied to the callus at time t_{0+} , i.e. the peak force registered at the beginning of the test. Thus, the total traction the callus is subjected to at time t is given by:

$$F(t) = \bar{G}(t) F_{t_{0+}} \quad (2)$$

A Prony series is commonly used for $\bar{G}(t)$, as in Comisso et al.⁶ and Calvo-Gallego et al.⁷. In this case, four terms were used:

$$\bar{G}(t) = g_{\infty} + \sum_{i=1}^3 g_i e^{-t/\tau_i} \quad (3)$$

normalized such that:

$$g_\infty + \sum_{i=1}^3 g_i = 1 \quad (4)$$

$F_{t_{0+}}$ was directly measured in Mora-Macías et al.⁵. Troyer et al.¹³ showed that, on a general basis, the curve fit is not unique if both sets of constants (g_i and τ_i) are the variables to be adjusted. On the contrary, they showed that uniqueness of the fit is only ensured if relaxation times are fixed *a priori*. Following Koolstra et al.¹⁴, we fix them in decades: $\tau_1 = 1$ s, $\tau_2 = 10$ s and $\tau_3 = 100$ s; which additionally allows a proper understanding of the progress of relaxation through different time scales. Doing so, g_i can be interpreted as the proportion of stress relaxed in the time scale delimited between τ_{i-1} and τ_i . The first relaxation time could not be smaller than 1 s, because this is approximately the time taken for the distraction step. The last relaxation time was 100 s, because the tests spanned less than 600 s. This way, relaxation occurring after τ_3 is taken into account with g_∞ .

The raw force signal, \bar{F} , was filtered using a moving average to eliminate signal noise. Fig. 2 shows an example of the raw (blue) and filtered (red) forces. The analytical force record F given by equation (2) was fitted to the resulting filtered force record, termed \tilde{F} , by minimizing the following quadratic error:

$$e = \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\tilde{F}(t_i) - F(t_i) \right)^2 \quad (5)$$

where N is the total number of points recorded during the test and t_i is the time corresponding to point i .

The fitting methodology was taken from Calvo-Gallego et al.⁷, being the core of the algorithm a least squares minimization. However, this is a local gradient-based method and therefore it can be sensitive to the initial guess in certain nonlinear problems. To avoid this, a genetic algorithm was implemented first to find a preliminary minimum. This

type of algorithms guarantees that the minimum is searched in the entire domain, though not necessarily fulfilling the optimality condition. So, this preliminary minimum was used as the initial guess in the local least squares minimization. The goodness of the least squares fit was evaluated by means of the coefficient of variation, CV (expressed in percentage):

$$CV = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{e}{N}}}{\mu_{\tilde{F}}} \times 100 \quad (6)$$

where $\mu_{\tilde{F}}$ is the average of the temporal record $\tilde{F}(t_i)$.

Once the curves of all sheep and days were fitted, linear regressions were calculated between each g_i and TEFO (in days), so to evaluate how the viscoelastic constants changed with time.

Results

In Fig. 3 two typical experimental curves are shown along with its fitted curve. The average CV is 5.45%.

Fig. 4 shows regressions between each g_i and TEFO in days. R^2 and p-values are also shown and it can be noticed that all the correlations were statistically significant, though TEFO could only explain a small percentage of the variation of the constant in some cases, such as g_2 (25%) or g_3 (15%). On the contrary, g_1 clearly decreases with TEFO, while g_∞ increases, being their variations explained by TEFO to a great extent (54% and 39% respectively).

Discussion

As can be seen from Fig. 3, the proposed viscoelastic model is able to accurately reproduce the relaxation force curves of callus tissue. Fig. 3 corresponds to the relaxation of a certain sheep after the distraction step performed at days 2 and 12. Similar adjustments were achieved for the different sheep and days.

Constants g_1 , g_2 and g_3 represent the proportion of force relaxed in the very short-, short- and mid-term, respectively,

while g_∞ represents the proportion of the force yet to be relaxed well after 100 s, that can be relaxed in the long-term or simply not be relaxed.

Relaxation after day 2 is very quick (see Fig. 3 A), because short-term relaxation, g_1 , dominates the first days following osteotomy. As TEFO passes, the peak force F_{t_0+} increases and relaxation becomes more gradual, i.e. slower in the short-term and more important in the mid-term. This is confirmed by the regression analysis between g_i and TEFO (see Fig. 4): the slope of g_1 -TEFO is negative and large, that of g_2 -TEFO negative and small, that of g_3 -TEFO positive and small and that of g_∞ -TEFO positive and large. Thus, it could be stated that g_1 is somehow turning into g_∞ as TEFO passes.

The fact that all these correlations were statistically significant clearly indicates that TEFO has a strong influence on the viscoelastic properties. Despite the variability of the results was large, a high percentage of that variability could be explained by a single factor, TEFO. At least for g_1 and g_∞ , because g_2 and g_3 seemed to be rather constant with time.

Linear regressions were used to analyse the tendencies of each parameter and to compare the relative importance and how they evolve over the TEFO, which was the objective of this analysis. However, it is important to note that if one wants to use the regression equation to estimate the value of the parameters, an exponential regression would be preferable for g_1 and g_2 above a certain TEFO value, for which the linear regression becomes negative, which is meaningless.

Conclusions

The viscoelastic model proposed in this work has a crucial advantage over the previously published models, and in particular over the one used in Mora-Macías et al.⁵, who obtained the experimental curves: fixing the relaxation times τ_i allows a more comprehensive analysis of the viscoelastic behaviour, by enabling the distinction between the different

time scales. This made possible to find out how relaxation is faster a few days after osteotomy to become slower and more gradual with time. This can be related to callus composition, which changes with time in such a way that is consistent with the former idea. Initially, contents of water and organic phase are predominant, being easy for the water to flow through the newly formed callus tissue. This fact would lead to a quick relaxation of stresses. As time passes, the mineral phase becomes more and more present¹⁵, so hindering water from flowing and slowing down relaxation, but making the tissue stiffer.

The longer the time between the osteotomy and the movement of the bone segment (i.e. the longer TEFO), the slower the stress relaxation, so forcing the callus to bear higher stresses during more time. This fact has an influence on the progression of tissue differentiation that needs to be investigated. A deeper insight into the viscoelastic behaviour of the callus and the evolution of those stresses may be very useful to improve current distraction protocols.

Declaration of conflicting interests

The author(s) declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship and/or publication of this article.

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Figure 1. Scheme of the bone with the fixator during bone transport, adapted from⁵ (for more details, see^{5,10,11,16}). The main elements of the system are: frames (a), proximal Schanz screws (b), guide bar (c), mobile bar (d), Steinmann Pins (f), distraction callus site (g), bone transport segment (h) and docking site (i). C1, C2, C3, C4, C5 and C6 are the load cells installed in the fixator, from which the force is calculated, as explained in⁵.

Figure 2. Raw force and filtered force.

Figure 3. Temporal evolution of the force applied to the callus (red) and the force fitted using the viscoelastic model (blue). The results for a certain sheep are shown after the distraction step at day 2 (A) and at day 12 (B).

Figure 4. Linear regression between g_1 (A), g_2 (B), g_3 (C), g_∞ (D) and TEFO (in days).